

ON THE ROAD TO SUSTAINABILITY: PAVING THE WAY FOR
OPERAS AS AN EFFICIENT OPEN SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES
SCHOLARLY COMMUNICATION RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE

Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results

DELIVERABLE 8.3

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Abstract

This document provides an introduction to the OPERAS-PLUS project's key exploitable results (KERs), including aspects such as the definition, value proposition, IP management, exploitation path and dissemination activities and adoption. It describes the methodology that will be used to capture individual project results and iterate and mature how each KER will be sustained beyond the life of the project. Updates of this initial document will be provided at M18 and M30.

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Executive summary

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure dedicated to support open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and the Humanities in the European Research Area (ERA). Designed as a distributed infrastructure, it entered into its preparatory phase and was incorporated as an AISBL (Belgian non-profit Association) in 2019. OPERAS was included as part of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap in 2021¹ and is now on its path to become operational as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)² in 2028 thanks to the support of the OPERAS-PLUS project.

A key objective within the OPERAS-PLUS project will be the dissemination and exploitation of project results are essential steps in the research and development process. The OPERAS-PLUS Dissemination and exploitation plan (PEDR) is therefore designed to describe the overall methodology as a guideline for the activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project, engaging with the community, reaching out to it as well as the activities to be carried out to enhance the successful exploitation of the project results.

There will be a number of individual results produced by OPERAS-PLUS that will each be tracked and continually analysed for identification of appropriate exploitation strategies. The initial Key Exploitable Results (KERs) identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project are:

1. KER1 – OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework
2. KER2 – OPERAS Innovation Lab
3. KER3 – OPERAS portfolio of services
4. KER4 – OPERAS user training framework
5. KER5 – OPERAS national nodes

OPERAS is a distributed infrastructure with many different services and activities, thus has the challenge of addressing the added value for all its stakeholders including internal (e.g. its members), external (e.g. SSH researchers, policy makers), a mix of both internal and external (e.g. projects, national consortia), and users of services (e.g. SSH researchers, authors, editors, libraries). Therefore, to reach these diverse stakeholders, different strategies need to be used such as tailoring the types of publications and material (i.e. scientific publications, policy briefs, blog posts), public events (i.e. conferences, workshops, webinars), as well as the channels (i.e. website, social media).

Each of the KERs will be assigned a "KER champion" to act as the central contact point

¹ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Research_Infrastructure_Consortium

for all issues that might arise related to this KER and content will be managed via the OPERAS-PLUS project information management system using Confluence.

Sustainability for each Key Exploitable Result will be individually assessed covering organisational, technical and financial aspects that are supported by the wider OPERAS quality and service management implementation based on the FitSM and ISO 9001 standards. These are just a few examples of how OPERAS' structure can potentially underpin any KER result from the project.

The OPERAS-PLUS dissemination and exploitation plan pulls together defined target audiences matched with tailored dissemination strategies and measures that combine specific key results and how each will be exploited. Further refinements and detailed plans will be made over the course of the project and reported on in future updates.

1. Introduction

The dissemination and exploitation of project results are essential steps in the research and development process. The OPERAS-PLUS Dissemination and exploitation plan (PEDR) is designed to describe the overall methodology across the OPERAS-PLUS project as a guideline for the activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project, engaging with the community, reaching out to it as well as the activities to be carried out to enhance the successful exploitation of the project results. The plan identifies the strategy for dissemination and exploitation and describes the various channels that the project uses for it. This plan is complemented by the communications strategy outlined in D8.1.

The PEDR is to be considered a living document. It will be updated during the project implementation and tailored to the project's needs and progress on demand. The current document is a first draft of the PEDR and will be updated at the end of each reporting period (M18, M30).

Overall, a successful exploitation and dissemination plan will ensure that the results of the project are widely available and can be used to their full potential, contributing to the advancement of knowledge and the development of new products and services.

Therefore, this document is structured as follows:

- Section 1: introduces the document and its structure, including a brief overview of the project.
- Section 2: describes the dissemination strategy, target audience and measures to be taken.
- Section 3: details the approach to exploitation along with the specific key exploitable results already identified, how IPR will be managed and sustainability will be achieved.
- Section 4: concludes the overall document.

1.1. OPERAS-PLUS in a Nutshell

OPERAS is the Research Infrastructure dedicated to support open scholarly communication for the Social Sciences and the Humanities in the European Research Area (ERA). Designed as a distributed infrastructure, it entered into its preparatory phase and was incorporated as an AISBL (Belgian non-profit Association) in 2019. OPERAS was included as part of the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) roadmap in 2021³ and is now on its path to become operational

³ <https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/>

as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC)⁴ in 2028. The OPERAS-PLUS project aims at supporting the development of the infrastructure in this ERIC preparatory phase and towards its implementation. The project takes on a list of activities to achieve this goal, the required outcomes, while addressing the wider expected impacts outlined in the INFRADEV call. In doing so, it serves the OPERAS community with its variety of small-sized stakeholders, which are committed to make open scholarly communication the default practice in Social Sciences and Humanities in the ERA. OPERAS-PLUS provides the opportunity to evolve an operational and efficient framework to fulfil the EC expectations of scientific excellence and to articulate them with the needs and objectives of the OPERAS community. These needs had already started to be identified and addressed in both previous and current projects such as OPERAS-D⁵, HIRMEOS⁶, OPERAS-P⁷, TRIPLE⁸, and COESO⁹. OPERAS-PLUS furthers the developments and provision of respective solutions, thus enhancing the excellence of scholarly communications in the European Research Area.

The overall objectives of the OPERAS-PLUS project are divided in several specific objectives (SOs), defined by the topic description, the recommendations provided by the ESFRI report, and the issues raised by the OPERAS General Assembly in 2021:

- (SO1) Develop and strengthen OPERAS governance structure, esp. financial, legal, and human resource management aspects of the infrastructure in a sustainable way, compliant with RI management best practices.
- (SO2) Support the establishment and development of OPERAS national nodes, set up and manage their relations as part of the OPERAS infrastructure.
- (SO3) Develop OPERAS portfolio of services by providing both required technology and a monitoring system for services development.
- (SO4) Maximise OPERAS' impact in the ERA and at international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure.

1.2. OPERAS-PLUS Impacts

To measure the potential scale and significance of OPERAS-PLUS impact, three Beneficiary Target Groups (BTG) are identified:

1. The organisations that provide services or undertake activities in the field of Social Sciences and Humanities open scholarly communication, constituting the

⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/European_Research_Infrastructure_Consortium

⁵ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/operas-d/>

⁶ <https://www.hirmeos.eu/>

⁷ <https://operas-eu.org/projects/past-projects/operas-p/>

⁸ <https://project.gotriple.eu/>

⁹ <https://coeso.hypotheses.org/>

- ‘OPERAS community’, actual and potential. (BTG1)
2. The end-users of the services provided by BTG1, e.g Social Sciences and Humanities researchers in the ERA. (BTG2)
 3. The Member States and Associated Countries in the ERA and their funding bodies that support or should support BTG1 on providing efficient services to BTG2. (BTG3)

The relations between the different BTGs are established as follows: BGT1 provides services to BTG2, is supported by BTG3, in coordination with other Research Infrastructures. Therefore, the initial impacts to each target group of the project are summarised as follows.

- BTG1:
 - New members onboarded in OPERAS
 - Support to more innovative scholarly communication services in OPERAS Lab innovative services
 - Improved coordination with Social Sciences and Humanities ESFRIs and other EU E-Infrastructures
- BTG2:
 - Access to Social Sciences and Humanities research outputs extended to Social Sciences and Humanities researchers through OPERAS services
 - SSH researchers uptake of the services
 - New Letters of Commitment (LoCs) from Member States/Associated Countries to support OPERAS construction phase
- BTG3:
 - Multi-annual investment plan for OPERAS towards financial sustainability
 - New Member States/Associated Countries onboarded

These initial stakeholders have been further expanded (See Section 2), while further objectives have been defined in the OPERAS overall strategy approved in 2022 and an implementation plan that is currently being finalised with specific actions, key results and corresponding Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

1.3. OPERAS-PLUS Results

In a programme guide by Horizon Europe¹⁰, the term “results” is defined as follows:

What is generated during the project implementation. This may include, for example, know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes,

¹⁰

https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf

demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. Most project results (inventions, scientific works, etc) are 'Intellectual Property', which may, if appropriate, be protected by formal 'Intellectual Property Rights'. Example: Successful large-scale demonstrator: trial with 3 airports of an advanced forecasting system for proactive airport passenger flow management).

There will be a number of individual results produced by OPERAS-PLUS, that will each be tracked and continually analysed for identification of appropriate exploitation strategies, but overall, the project will focus on identifying and articulating Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The initial KERs identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project, are summarised below, with further details on each are provided in Section 3:

1. KER1 - OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework
2. KER2 - OPERAS Innovation Lab
3. KER3 - OPERAS portfolio of services
4. KER4 - OPERAS user training framework
5. KER5 - OPERAS national nodes

2. Dissemination

Dissemination is a crucial step in research and development because it allows the findings and outcomes of a project to be shared with other researchers, practitioners, and the general public. One of the OPERAS Pillars – empowering of the community – dictates communication and outreach activities provide the basis for the dissemination and exploitation efforts. As the profile of the OPERAS RI pertains to the different communities, projects related to OPERAS, such as TRIPLE, COESO, CRAFT-OA, PALOMERA, and DIAMAS, amongst others, will enable the exploitation and foster the engagement within growing communities. The internal community building is supported by WP3, and the building of communication networks is supported by WP8.

The latter (WP8) is at the heart of communication and will be responsible for the coordination of all different activities, starting with the gathering of the project results, then disseminating them to the various target groups. This will also include the alignment with communication activities organised by parallel projects (like those previously mentioned) and stakeholders in OPERAS. Examples of stakeholders are those involved in the Special Interest Groups (SIGs) and the activities of the national nodes (WP7) as well as the services (WP5) and Innovation Lab (WP4), all of which were already established in the OPERAS-P project, but will be more specifically defined to

guarantee a better uptake of the different communication activities of the various national communities and diverse target groups of the growing RI. All respective outputs will be available as soon as possible as preprints and will be later on presented in an open access format to ensure limitless access.

As part of WP8, the list of metrics and KPIs will be systematically collected to ensure clarity of understanding and matched to the expectations and perceptions of our stakeholders, users, and service providers. It will allow the project to precisely assess the impact of the OPERAS RI and provide timely and accurate information to its governance bodies (i.e. Executive and General Assemblies), enabling them to steer the evolution of the strategy and take informed decisions.

2.1. Dissemination Strategy

The OPERAS-PLUS Communication Strategy (D8.1) provides a more detailed guide for all communication activities and dissemination measures of the OPERAS RI and delineates how communication and dissemination can contribute to exploitation. As the OPERAS-PLUS project mainly supports the development of the OPERAS RI and its preparatory phase towards becoming an ERIC, the strategy is therefore focused on the final objectives of the infrastructure as a whole.

The strategic aim is to increase awareness and visibility of the OPERAS RI, the products/services it is developing, and its activities. This strategy mainly addresses external communication for the OPERAS RI, focusing on:

- Raising awareness of the RI
- Increasing understanding of the RI's operations
- Fostering international collaboration by connecting different scientific communities, as well as societal and economic actors, on an international level
- Building commitment by the target audience to the goals and objectives
- Raising awareness of the services catalogue to better deliver the services to the different stakeholders
- Promoting innovations in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) by fostering the OPERAS Innovation Lab
- Advocating for Open Science and the Diamond Open Access Model
- Communicating about EU-Funding.

One objective of the OPERAS-PLUS project is to maximise OPERAS' impact in the European Research Area (ERA) and at the international level by extending it beyond its current scope and onboarding new members and countries in the infrastructure. It is

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important to empower all OPERAS national nodes, members, and project participants to present OPERAS on different occasions by providing a toolbox and manuals. The approach of Work Package 8 is to structure communication strategies and open the OPERAS communication channels to be used for the different OPERAS activities to grow the audience.

As mentioned, the OPERAS Strategic Plan (2023–2025), approved in 2022, extended the strategic objectives to 9, which cover:

- Objective 1: OPERAS as a pan-European, efficient organisation and highly representative of the SSH Open ScholComm communities
- Objective 2: The Diamond model supported as a major one in the scholarly communication ecosystem (gov & coordination + supporting bibliodiversity)
- Objective 3: OPERAS services published and integrated with EOSC and other marketplaces and communities (regional, national, international)
- Objective 4: Clear set of well-defined and operational services (portfolio of services + fostering quality)
- Objective 5: OPERAS members and communities are trained and knowledgeable in SSH FAIR and Open Science practices (training + empowering com):
- Objective 6: OPERAS members are trained and knowledgeable in SSH open science service delivery
- Objective 7: OPERAS as a trusted advisor for national and European OS strategies (policy advising + ecosystem)
- Objective 8: Academic books are included in the Open Science policies
- Objective 9: Setting up a pan-European OPERAS innovation lab

2.2. Targets

In addition to the broad target groups introduced in Section 1, a more specific breakdown can be derived in order to have more tailored messaging and targeted outreach. As OPERAS is a complex infrastructure, with many different services and activities, it has the challenge of addressing the added value for all its stakeholders.

Our target audiences can be categorised as follows:

- Internal stakeholders
- External stakeholders
- Mix of both internal and external
- Customers/users of services

2.2.1. Internal stakeholders

- OPERAS Members
- General Assembly
- Special Interest Group members
- The Scientific Advisory Committee
- The Executive Assembly
- OPERAS services providers

2.2.2. External stakeholders

- SSH researchers
- Research policymakers, European Commission, European Member States and Associated Countries
- Publishers
- Research performing organisations
- Scholarly communication service providers (e.g. infrastructure providers etc.)
- Libraries and librarians
- European Research Infrastructures/other SSH ESFRIs (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures)/E-Infrastructures
- Research funding organisations, funders
- Civil society organisations
- Public/Broader audience/citizens

2.2.3. Internal and External stakeholders

- Projects consortia (OPERAS-PLUS, TRIPLE, COESO, DIAMAS, PALOMERA, CRAFT-OA, GraspOS, etc.)
- National communities

2.2.4. Customers/users of services

- SSH Researchers
- Authors
- Editors, Editorial Managers
- Publishers
- Libraries
- Service Providers
- Translators

2.3. Dissemination Measures

There will be a number of measures to be taken throughout the project that will be based on the following key communication objectives:

- Raise more awareness of the infrastructure among all its stakeholders and potential stakeholders
- Explain what the infrastructure is, the services provided, the projects running and the people involved
- Promote events, publications and initiatives related to the infrastructure and its members
- Increase the network, reaching out to potential new members
- Increase the community's engagement and open the possibility for dialogue
- Keep the community updated about the latest actions of the infrastructure and its projects.

The following table describes the dissemination measures aimed for promoting the infrastructure and its activities planned for the OPERAS-PLUS project:

Target audience	Means of dissemination		
	Publications and other dissemination material	Public events/ presentations	Communication Channels
SSH researchers	Scientific publications, Blog posts, OPERAS Innovation Lab Observatory Website Reports	OPERAS Conference, Workshops	OPERAS Website, Twitter, OPERAS Lab Observatory Website, Instagram, Youtube, marketing campaign
Research Policymakers/Member States	Policy Briefs, OPERAS Innovation Lab Observatory, FAIR Training, Annual Report, Fact Sheet	Small Workshops dedicated to introduce the policy briefs	OPERAS Website, Twitter, LinkedIn, press releases,
Publishers	Flyer, Policy briefs, Factsheet on	OPERAS Conference, presentations at	OPERAS Website, Twitter,

	services, Blog posts	events	LinkedIn, Youtube
Libraries and librarians	Flyer, Policy briefs, Factsheet on services, blog posts, scientific publications	OPERAS Conference, presentations at events, workshops	OPERAS Website, mailing lists, Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube, press releases
Research Performing Organisations	Flyer, scientific publications, factsheets on services, blog posts	Conference, presentations at external events, workshops	Website, OPERAS Innovation Lab Observatory Website, LinkedIn, Twitter, press releases,
Infrastructure service providers	Flyer, scientific publications, factsheets on services, Blog posts	Conferences and public events, workshops	OPERAS Website, mailing lists, press releases, Twitter, LinkedIn
Research funding organisations/Funders	Policy Briefs, Scientific Publications, Innovation Lab Observatory, Annual Report	Conferences and public events, Workshops	Website, Press releases, LinkedIn, Twitter
Society/Socio-economic actors/citizens	Blog Posts		Website, Instagram, Twitter, Youtube

Table 1: Target audience and means of dissemination

3. Exploitation

Exploitation means the use of results in further research and innovation activities other than those covered by the action concerned, including inter alia, commercial exploitation such as developing, creating, manufacturing and marketing a product or process, creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.

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3.1. Approach

For clarity for both consortium members as well as external stakeholders, it is important to distinguish between project results and key exploitable results.

3.1.1. Project results

Project results are generated during the project implementation. This may include: know-how, innovative solutions, algorithms, proof of feasibility, new business models, policy recommendations, guidelines, prototypes, demonstrators, databases and datasets, trained researchers, new infrastructures, networks, etc. They also include research roadmaps, policy recommendations, reports, platforms (collaboration), skills and knowledge, educational materials, codes of conduct, pre-standards, prototypes, software, publications and data.

3.1.2. Key Exploitable Results (KERs)

The primary project results from the dissemination and exploitation point of view are the Key Exploitable Results (KER). A specific note from the EC Portal states that before uploading a result in the Horizon Results Platform, to make sure that it is in fact a Key Exploitable Result, which defines a KER as: "Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights".

Therefore, OPERAS-PLUS is prioritising the identification of the main interesting results (as defined above), which have been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" – meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.

The following criteria is used to select and prioritise these results:

- degree of innovation
- exploitability
- impact

3.1.3. KER Champion

For further refining and consolidating the collection of information required to fully analyse, articulate and disseminate, each of the KERs will be assigned a "KER

champion". The role of the KER champion is to act as the central contact point for all issues that might arise related to this KER. The champion also helps to coordinate and encourage the exploitation and dissemination of the KER. The champion also acts as the primary spokesperson for the KER and accepts or suggests changes and improvements of the KER-related documentation, promotional material, and plans in collaboration with the different WP8 team members.

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3.1.4. Confluence

The OPERAS-PLUS project management has selected Confluence¹¹ as its solution for its information management system to provide a full knowledge base. Confluence also offers a number of functionalities that support not only static collection of information, but also supports the management of several project activities such as deliverables and milestones, action assignment as well as the use of templates that can be used to harmonise content.

For management of both project objectives and KERs, a dedicated section of the project Confluence space has been dedicated to this activity, with a template having already been structured based on the Horizon Results Platform required set of information (i.e. Result Title, Target Audiences and Needs; About us; Result Description and Influence; Result and Business Maturity and exploitation outlook; and Investors Corner).

This approach offers the ability for information to be collaboratively worked on, always transparent in its availability, while ensuring that the right information can be easily imported into the portal by project’s end.

Image 1: Screenshot of project results and KERs in Confluence

¹¹ <https://www.atlassian.com/software/confluence>

Image 2: Screenshot of KER template in Confluence

3.1.5. Horizon results booster service

Several consortium partners have had experience from previous projects (i.e. TRIPLE) running through the Horizon Results Booster¹² service that offers expert, free of charge, support services to boost the exploitation potential of research results, disseminate effectively, and go to market. There are 3 different modules offered: Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy, Business Plan Development, and Go To Market.

It is expected that the initial use of the available templates will help guide the KER Champions to better articulate their exploitation plans. A formal request of the service will be evaluated as the project develops.

3.2. Key Exploitable Results

As mentioned in Section 1, there will be a number of individual results produced by OPERAS-PLUS, that will each be tracked and continually analysed for identification of appropriate exploitation strategies, but overall, the project will focus on identifying and articulating Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The initial KERs identified in the project preparation phase, and revised in the first months of the project, are detailed in this section.

¹² <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

3.2.1. KER1 – OPERAS core governance, finance and management framework

This KER covers the overarching governance and sustainability of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure as it moves towards becoming an ERIC. Therefore the individual results are combined into a single KER with dedicated exploitation plans as follows:

- The compliance and/or certification of the OPERAS ERIC with quality, IT service and risk management ISO standards.
- An Initial legal framework and financial multiannual plan to prepare for the transition towards an ERIC
- Updated governance model, including relationships with private and commercial entities
- Prototype and update the Business Model to support the long-term sustainability of OPERAS
- An equal opportunity pan-European employment framework with a specific focus on the gender equality plan and the “no asshole” rule, including the applicability of RESAVER¹³.
- Develop and implement a risk management framework and capacity plan.
- Update medium and long-term strategic plans

Key Results and Related Actions

- ERIC Statutes and legal documents submitted to the EC for approval
 - Prepare OPERAS ERIC governance model
 - Initial OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.1)
 - Updated OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.5)
 - Final OPERAS Governance framework & Strategy Implementation Plan (D2.8)
 - Prepare legal and financial framework of OPERAS ERIC
 - Initial OPERAS Legal & Financial framework (D2.2)
 - Final OPERAS Legal & Financial framework (D2.9)
 - Submit the legal and financial framework for approval and adoption (D3.3)
 - Define human resources framework
 - Initial OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.3)
 - Final OPERAS pan-European Human Resources policy (D2.6)

¹³ <https://www.resaver.eu/>

3.2.2. KER2 – OPERAS Innovation Lab

The OPERAS Innovation Lab aims at strengthening prototyping innovative and FAIR services for the Social Sciences and Humanities community. Supported by WP4, to put into practice the recommendations stemming from the Future of Scholarly Communication report¹⁴, that was prepared in the OPERAS-P project through extensive research into OPERAS user needs. The general objective is to establish the OPERAS Innovation Lab as the knowledge hub for the OPERAS community, providing guidelines and counselling to stakeholders wishing to engage with innovative outputs, as well liaising between those stakeholders and relevant e-infrastructure providers. The objectives are to:

- Structure the Innovation Lab within OPERAS by establishing working relationships with OPERAS members and other e-infrastructure providers, who may provide services for innovative and FAIR outputs
- Provide coherent and up-to-date knowledge on innovations to the OPERAS community
- Support and sustain innovative outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities disciplines
- Strengthen the prestige of innovative publications through prototyping their evaluation

Key Results and Related Actions

- The Innovation Lab is defined
 - Set up internal research seminar
 - Prepare the Innovation Lab Terms of Reference (ToR)
- OPERAS-PLUS WP4 outputs have been delivered
 - Guidelines on publishing and evaluating innovative outputs in Social Sciences and Humanities (D4.1)
 - Organise community validation workshop (MS7)
 - Develop evaluation framework for innovative outputs (T4.3)
- An OPERAS Innovation fund is set-up
 - Define the scope and the budget envelope of the innovation fund
 - Communicate about the Innovation Fund
 - Launch call(s) for participation

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>

3.2.3. KER3 – OPERAS portfolio of services

The OPERAS portfolio of services aims at structuring and developing the OPERAS services in the specific context of OPERAS being a distributed infrastructure. Designed during the OPERAS-D project, initiated in the course of the OPERAS-P project, OPERAS catalogue of service needs further work to gain consistency and start operating, according to the principle “as FAIR as possible”. The specific objectives are to:

- Establish the legal, organisational, contractual framework needed to obtain a working catalogue of services
- Integrate more OPERAS services into the EOSC and related catalogues of services (SSHOC, OpenAIRE)
- Give dedicated support for the development of current services identified in the OPERAS-D and OPERAS-P design study
- Leverage on the FAIRification tools and process as suggested by the community in WP3 and WP4
- Achieve design studies to prepare the development of future services

Key Results and Related Actions

- OPERAS Integrated Management System initial version operational
 - Create initial structure
 - Provide access to relevant members
 - Populate with initial content
- Service strategy and roadmap published
 - Publish an annual service strategy and roadmap
- Business models for all current and new services (incl. licensing models) established
 - Service Design and Transition Packages (SDTP) available for all services
- Service reviews, including capacity requirements (e.g. sustainability) conducted
 - Prepare service review template
 - Conduct service review
- FitSM organisation certification achieved and retained
 - Conduct initial IMS Maturity Assessment
 - Conduct internal audit of OPERAS Integrated management system
 - Conduct certification audit against FitSM
 - Conduct internal audit of OPERAS Integrated management system
 - Conduct surveillance audit against FitSM

3.2.4. KER4 – OPERAS user training framework

The overall objective of this KER is to deliver a methodological framework that has been developed, tested, and applied for continuous evaluation of user engagement with OPERAS services, based upon explicit understanding of users, goals, tasks, resources and environments, and by applying state-of-the-art usability and user experience knowledge and methods. This includes an established framework for the development of adequate open science and scholarly communication training that meets the users' and other stakeholders' needs and requirements. This would ensure the user-centeredness and sustainability of existing and future research infrastructure (RI) services. All tasks will take into account issues of multiculturalism, multilingualism and FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse).

Key Results and Related Actions

- Developed OPERAS Training strategy
 - Identification of opportunities for facilitating and performing training
 - Identification of relevant training area
 - Identification of relevant targeted user groups
 - Identification of training providers
 - Description of training activities
- Designed Competence Center for Social Sciences and Humanities
 - Preparation of Open Science, FAIR and RDM learning path for SSH
 - Recommendation of actions for the set-up of Open Science and RDM thematic trainings
- Integrated dissemination of Knowledge into OPERAS Communication
 - Common framework defining the methodology for achieving user-centred quality objectives (D6.1)
 - Report on implementation of the methodological framework for user-centred quality on selected services (D6.2)
 - Framework for the development of open science and scholarly communication training (D6.3)
- Knowledge acquired in IT Service Management using FitSM (lightweight ITSM standard) as the reference framework Ensure inclusion in the training strategy
 - Identify (new) opportunities for organising training courses
 - Organise courses
- Knowledge acquired on the individual services offered by OPERAS
 - Ensure inclusion in the training strategy
 - Conduct webinars and/or hands-on trainings
- OPERAS services alignment with EOSC and FAIR requirements webinar or

- presentation
- Ensure inclusion in the training strategy
 - Conduct webinars or presentation
 - OPERAS Integrated Management System for Federation Members webinar and/or presentation
 - Ensure inclusion in the training strategy
 - Conduct webinars or presentation
 - Services and service delivery models in SSH open science webinar and/or presentation
 - Ensure inclusion in the training strategy
 - Conduct webinars or presentation

3.2.5. KER5 – OPERAS national nodes

This KER deals with the implementation of OPERAS national nodes and the framing of their connection with the central hub. National nodes play a pivotal role in establishing a connection point to outside the OPERAS community, in promoting a proximity relation with local communities, helping to identify needs, provide services, and training. They are in a decisive position to find a balanced solution for the keeping of national languages as fully scientific valid modes of expression, while promoting them on the international level. This strategy is fully aligned with the paths to outreach beyond Europe, and with the development and implementation of the GoTriple platform, benefiting directly from a future service dedicated to supporting translations and stimulating cross-publications.

Key Results and Related Actions

- Established OPERAS national nodes for each member of the EA
 - Sharing good practices
 - Internal WP Kick-off meeting with prospective National Nodes (MS2)
 - National node can be used as regional node when needed and no linguistic barrier exist
 - Mapping opportunities, needs and challenges: OPERAS and the potential national nodes (D7.1)
 - Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes (D7.2)
 - Roadmap for the Implementation of OPERAS national nodes – Final (D7.3)
 - Formalising and securing relations between hub and nodes
 - Aligning Hub and National Node governance

3.3. IPR Management

Intellectual property management is the management of an organisation's intellectual property (IP), including patents, trademarks, copyrights, and trade secrets. The goal of IP management is to maximise the value of an organisation's IP while minimising the associated risks, costs, and administrative burdens. IP management activities include protecting IP, licensing and monetizing IP, and leveraging IP to create new products and services.

The OPERAS-PLUS Consortium Agreement remains the reference document for handling of IPR, whether as background or as foreground. However, any result of research, work, publication or invention that derives from the activities carried out within the scope of the OPERAS-PLUS project and is susceptible to economic exploitation or may give rise to a request for ownership of intellectual property rights, the project management (WPI) shall be notified including the beneficiary representative. IPR will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis as necessary.

In addition, IPR will be explicitly analysed as part of the KER business and sustainability model.

3.4. Sustainability

To ensure organisational, technical and financial sustainability for each Key Exploitable Results will be individually assessed. However, as it is OPERAS' mission to coordinate and federate resources in Europe to efficiently address the scholarly communication needs of European researchers in the field of SSH, having a legal and administrative option is a natural channel to be initially explored.

Something that has already been taken advantage of with the GoTriple service as one of the main KERs from the TRIPLE project, where OPERAS serves as the legal host while also supporting the agreement structure.

It is important to note that OPERAS has 3 types of services as part of its portfolio: Managed, Community, and Internal.

- Managed services are when OPERAS is responsible for the overall service and coordination of the service delivery and evolution. This provides value when a sustainable structure is required and/or is strategic for OPERAS.
- Community services are services that are discoverable from the OPERAS website,

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but are managed directly by the community provider. This is valuable when there is a sustainable structure established and amplification along with direct OPERAS participation, contribution, support is beneficial.

- Internal services are not orderable, but are necessary for managing or operating the OPERAS federation. These comprise both technical and non-technical services that must still be managed though not requestable by those outside of the federation.

OPERAS' strategy is to find a balance between the types of services that match available resources as it grows over time.

GoTriple¹⁵ is a perfect example of OPERAS' mission to not only make Open Science a reality for research in SSH, but also benefits as a managed service where the legal entity established (OPERAS AISBL) provides a solid legal and administrative support, along with the value add brought around dissemination, communication, community engagement, and service management support. This organisation has been formalised via the definition of a Memorandum of Understanding, including a Terms of Reference, which outlines both the management and coordination of the service as well as the commitment of the various partners to continue to actively contribute to maintaining and evolving the service and community.

In addition to the organisation aspects, in order to keep GoTriple technically sustainable after the project ends, we conducted a categorisation of GoTriple into service components with specifications of each comprising: type (enabling, enhancing), short description, service component provider, and technology readiness level (TRL). Within this activity, we identified 18 service components, provided by 12 different providers. Agreements are being established between OPERAS and each component provider (supplier) to ensure that each component will be provided beyond the life of the project. The names of the agreements will depend on the type of supplier (i.e. Operational Level Agreements with internal suppliers, Underpinning Agreements or Contracts with external suppliers). This agreement structure, methodology, and terminology follow the FitSM lightweight service management standard that is being used as the underlying framework.

An embedded activity as part of the IT service management implementation, and more specifically in Service Portfolio Management, is how any new or updated service is captured, assessed and approved, which is through the use of Service Design and Transition Packages (SDTP). A core component of this structured SDTP document is the identification and articulation of appropriate business models that can support the

¹⁵ <https://www.gotriple.eu/>

sustainability of the given services. These are just a few examples of how OPERAS' structure can potentially underpin any KER result from the project. Though it does not necessarily have to be the mechanism that is used, it represents the possibility for KER to be continuously exploited where needed.

4. Conclusion

OPERAS is a distributed Research Infrastructure that supports open scholarly communication in the Social Sciences and the Humanities in the European Research Area that has a diverse set of stakeholders. To address this challenge, OPERAS-PLUS will use different strategies tailored to each group, which has been outlined in this report. The dissemination and exploitation of project results are not only essential steps in the research and development process, but crucial in communicating what will ultimately be delivered to them. Therefore, this initial dissemination and exploitation plan combined specific key results and tailored dissemination strategies and measures to ensure successful uptake of the project results.

Over the course of the project, the Key Exploitable Results (KERs) that were identified in the project preparation phase will be individually assessed for sustainability and exploitation, which will be systematically captured as part of the OPERAS-PLUS project information management system.

This report has laid out the initial plans designed to provide a guideline for the activities of all project partners when sharing information about the project. The next steps will be to work directly with the individual KER Champions for the initial population of content associated with each, while also continuing to engage project management and the wider consortium for the identification of potential new KERs.

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